

EVALUATION OF ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR SST STRUCTURES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES AND AFTER THERMAL AGING

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SUMMARY: The objective of this experimental study was to evaluate the effect of thermal aging on the ultimate strength of three kinds of carbon/high-temperature polymer composite materials, which are current candidate structural materials for a super sonic transport of the next generation. The notched and unnotched panels, before being machined to specimens, were aged at 120°C and 180°C for up to 15,000 hours. Static tests at room and elevated temperatures before and after thermal aging provided the notched tensile, notched compressive, and short beam shear strengths. Moreover, the effects of five oxidation resistant treatments on notched compressive strength at 180°C were investigated after thermal aging of 5,000 hours at 180°C. The obtained results were presented and a possibility to develop an accelerated environment test methodology is examined.

KEYWORDS: bismaleimide composites, thermoplastic polyimide composite, super sonic transport, notched strengths, short beam shear strength, thermal aging, oxidation resistant treatments, accelerated test methodology

INTRODUCTION

The structures of super sonic transports (SST) of the next generation require long term durability of structural materials in environments that include temperature, loads, and fluids, not only in constant states, but also during cyclic fluctuations. Moreover, the structural weights must be drastically reduced to achieve commercial success. This requirement demands a wide application of high temperature polymer composite materials.

Many fundamental studies have been conducted for investigating oxidation, micro-cracking, and weight loss by thermal aging, creep, etc. on high temperature polymer composites.

However, only a few results [1,2] are found suitable to directly evaluate their practicality for the SST structures.

As a part of structural material evaluation for a SST of the next generation, this study investigated the strength degradation of high temperature composites by thermal aging, the effects of oxidation resistant treatments, and a possibility to establish accelerated test methodology to simulate environmental conditions encountered by SSTs in their lives. Namely, the tensile and compressive strengths of notched specimens, and the short beam shear (SBS) strength were investigated for three kinds of carbon/high-temperature polymer composites at room and elevated temperatures, before and after thermal aging of up to 15,000 hours. In addition, composite panels were given five kinds of oxidation resistant treatments and thermally aged. The effects of these treatments on notched compressive strength were examined. The obtained test results are evaluated and the possibility of developing an accelerated test method is discussed using a modified Larson-Miller type equation.

MATERIALS, SPECIMENS, AND TEST PROCEDURE

The three kinds of carbon/high temperature polymer composite laminates tested were made of two kinds of carbon/bismaleimide prepreg systems, G40-800/5260 (NARMCO) and MR50K/MR2000N (Mitsubishi Rayon Co.), and a carbon/amorphous thermoplastic polyimide prepreg system, T800H/PI-SP (Mitsui Toatsu Co.), which are current candidate composites for the SST structures.

The two kinds of panels with quasi isotropic stacking sequences, 24 plies $(45/0/-45/90)_{3S}$ for tensile notched specimens, and 32 plies $(45/0/-45/90)_{4S}$ for compressive notched specimens, were circular-hole notched before thermal aging. The panels for SBS specimens were a unidirectional laminate, 20 plies $(0)_{20}$. These panels were isothermally aged for 5,000, 10,000, and 15,000 hours at 120°C or 180°C in air circulating ovens. Specimens were machined from virgin and thermally aged panels. Figure 1 shows the geometry of panels for thermal aging and specimens tested.

Fig. 1: Geometry of panels for thermal aging and specimens tested; dimensions in mm

Prior to static tests, specimens were dried in a vacuum oven for 6 hours at 70°C and then for 144 hours at 110°C. Static tests were conducted at room and thermal aging temperatures. Moreover, the surfaces of the MR50K/MR2000N panels were given five kinds of oxidation resistant treatments. The effects of these treatments on notched compressive strength at 180°C were investigated after thermal aging of 5,000 hours at 180°C.

The notched tensile and notched compressive strengths are represented by nominal strength calculated using the nominal thickness based on the nominal prepreg thickness and the net width. The SBS strength is represented by net strength calculated using the measured thickness.

TEST RESULTS

Notched Tensile Strength of G40-800/5260 Composite After Thermal Aging

Two batches of G40-800/5260 laminates were produced, and four specimens were used for each test. Figure 2 presents the relationship between notched tensile strength and thermal aging time separated by the batches A and B. The presence of the strength degradation by thermal aging at 120°C is not clear. It is a future problem to elucidate that the obtained results are within a scatter band, or that the strength slightly decreases with thermal aging time. In the case of thermal aging at 180°C, fairly large strength degradation appeared. Thermal aging time over 15,000 hours is necessary to know if the strength degradation will saturate like in metallic materials [3]. The strengths at room and thermal aging temperatures, at the same aging time, are close for either thermal aging at 120°C or 180°C. A small difference between the two batches of specimens appeared in the strength and degradation with thermal aging time, as shown in Fig. 2.

There is no example to show the large scatter in notched tensile strengths observed for each experimental condition, i.e., a combination of test temperature, aging temperature, and thermal aging time.

Fig. 2: Notched tensile strength of G40-800/5260 carbon/bismaleimide composite versus thermal aging time for two batches A and B

Notched Compressive Strength After Thermal Aging

Figure 3 shows the relationships between notched compressive strength and thermal aging time for the three kinds of high temperature polymer composites. Five specimens were used for each test in Fig. 3, except for a special case.

In the case of the G40-800/5260 bismaleimide composite and thermal aging at 120°C, the strength at room temperature does not reduce with thermal aging time, but that at 120°C slightly reduces. In the case of 180°C aging, the strength remarkably decreases with thermal aging time, and after 5,000 hours, this drop is almost proportional to thermal aging time. A similar trend of the notched compressive strength of a IM7/5260 composite at room temperature was reported by Rogalski [1]. The difference of the strengths at room and thermal aging temperatures at the same aging time are fairly large for thermal aging at both 120°C and 180°C. This is different from the notched tensile strength in Fig. 2.

In the case of the MR50K/MR2000N bismaleimide composite and thermal aging at 120°C, the strength at 120°C shows a slight drop after thermal aging of 15,000 hours. In the case of thermal aging at 180°C, the strength significantly decreases with thermal aging time. The strength degradation is especially great from 5,000 to 10,000 hours, and dulls after 10,000 hours.

In the case of the T800H/PI-SP polyimide composite, non-aged strengths at room temperature and 180°C are slightly lower in comparison with those of the other two materials. However, the strength degradation by thermal aging at 120°C and 180°C, up to 15,000 hours, was not found.

There is no example to show the large scatter in notched compressive strengths observed for each experimental condition and the three materials.

Fig. 3: Notched compressive strength versus thermal aging time for three kinds of high temperature composites

Short Beam Shear Strength After Thermal Aging

In SBS tests, various behaviors appeared in the relationship between the central displacement of a SBS specimen and load, according to the combination of material, test temperature, thermal aging temperature, and thermal aging time. Therefore, it was difficult to physically define the SBS strength in a way common to all cases. The SBS strength in this study is represented by the maximum stress which can be commonly determined for all test cases, though this definition is questionable as a SBS strength.

Figure 4 depicts the obtained results of SBS strength versus thermal aging time for three kinds of high temperature composites. The test number is fundamentally five for each case.

In these cases, for both carbon/bismaleimide composites, the SBS strengths at room temperature and at 120°C, did not drop after thermal aging at 120°C. The SBS strengths of the G40-800/5260 composite at room temperature and 180°C, after thermal aging at 180°C, reduced with fluctuations. In this material, the difference of strengths at room and thermal aging temperatures, at the same aging time, are large for thermal aging at both 120°C and 180°C. This difference is largest among the notched tensile, notched compressive, and SBS strengths, as presented in Figs. 2, 3, and 4.

The SBS strength of the MR50K/MR2000N composite at 180°C indicated a fairly large drop with thermal aging time. The scatter of the SBS strength was high after the thermal aging at 180°C.

In the case of the T800H/PI-SP composite, there was no reduction of the SBS strength after thermal aging at 120°C and 180°C.

Fig. 4: Short beam shear (SBS) strength versus thermal aging time for three kinds of high temperature composites

Effect of Oxidation Resistant Treatment on Notched Compressive Strength

The notched compressive strength of the MR50K/MR2000N composite was heavily reduced by thermal aging at 180°C, as shown in Fig. 3. With respect to this material, the following oxidation resistant treatments against circulating hot air were given to the panels to be

thermally aged, and the effects of these treatments on notched compressive strength were investigated. Six panels of a new batch were made. They were of the same size indicated in Fig. 1, and their surfaces and sections were given the following oxidation resistant treatments. **A**: no treatment given to get base data, **B**: holes were bolted, **C**: holes and sections were sealed by a bismaleimide resin, **D**: full surfaces and sections were painted by a thermal protection paint, **E**: only holes and sections were painted by the same paint, **F**: covered by a glass fiber cloth. The main element of the thermal protection paint used was silicon.

Notched compressive specimens were machined from each panel after thermal aging of 5,000 hours at 180°C. Compression tests were conducted at 180°C. Each case was tested four times and the results obtained are presented in Fig. 5. In order to compare these results with the strengths obtained at room temperature with no thermal aging, and those at 180°C after thermal aging of 5,000 hours at 180°C in Fig. 3, the data of Fig. 3 were also plotted in Fig. 5.

The strengths at 180°C of the unprotected panels from different batches after the thermal aging are slightly different. This is considered to originate from the difference of the two batches. The strength of the unprotected panel **A** and those of the protected panels **B**, **D**, **E**, and **F** are almost equal. Therefore, the protections **B**, **D**, **E**, and **F** had no effect on notched compressive strength. The protection **C** improved the average strength to only approximately 10% higher than those of the other cases. This indicates a very important fact that if an appropriate protection method is selected, the strength degradation can be improved.

Fig. 5: Effect of oxidation resistant treatment on the notched compressive strength of MR50K/MR2000N carbon/bismaleimide composite

DISCUSSION

Characteristics of High Temperature Composite Materials

In the case of two kinds of bismaleimide composites, microscopic observation of the surfaces and sections indicated that the degradation by thermal aging at 180°C was produced mainly by the matrix oxidation and micro-cracking in and inter the layers. No significant degradation caused by thermal aging at 120°C was found on the panels of both bismaleimide composites.

The upper limit of applicable temperature for both bismaleimide composites is considered to be higher than 120°C, but lower than 180°C. It is necessary to find the upper limit between the two temperatures. Moreover, the notched compressive strength of these materials at 120°C, after thermal aging at 120°C, indicated a trend of slight degradation. Meanwhile, Rogalski presented no degradation of the notched compressive strength of the IM7/5260 bismaleimide composite at room temperature after thermal aging of 16,000 hours at 149°C [1]. In order to discern this problem, it is necessary to conduct static tests at elevated temperatures after thermal aging longer than 15,000 hours.

In the G40-800/5260 composite, the ascending order of the strength differences at room and aging temperatures, at the same aging time, is notched tensile strength, notched compressive strength, and SBS strength.

Figures 3 and 4 present promising results for the T800H/PI-SP thermoplastic polyimide composite; however, micro-cracks were observed after thermal aging at 120°C and 180°C in both outer and inner layers. To prevent micro-cracking is an issue of vital importance for this material.

In comparison of the test results in Fig. 4 with those in Fig. 3, the degradation tendency in notched compressive strength and SBS strength is a bit different for both bismaleimide composites after thermal aging at 180°C. However, the notched compressive strength did not drop when no degradation appeared in the SBS strength, such as the SBS strength at room temperature and 120°C, after thermal aging at 120°C, and those of T800H/PI-SP composite at 120°C and 180°C, after thermal aging at 120°C and 180°C respectively. These results provide a rough suggestion that no degradation of SBS strength means no degradation in notched compressive strength.

A large scatter in the data points was observed in the SBS strength of the MR50K/MR2000N composite after thermal aging at 180°C. Except for these cases, the scatter of test results is considerably small.

Application of a Modified Larson-Miller Equation in Analyzing the Strength After Thermal Aging

Shimokawa and Katoh modified Larson-Miller's equation, which is generally applied in analyzing the creep strength of metals, as

$$\ln S = (a + b \cdot T) + (c + d \cdot T) \ln L, \quad (1)$$

and used to analyze the strength of light metallic materials after thermal aging [3]. Strength is denoted by S , temperature by T , aging time by L . a , b , c , and d are parameters. Original Larson-Miller's equation is given by $c=0$.

Equation (1) indicates that if T is constant, $\ln S$ and $\ln L$ have a linear relationship. If at least the test results satisfy this relationship, an accelerated thermal aging test can be performed. The test results given in Figs. 2, 3, and 4 are separately plotted on double logarithmic graph paper, though they are not presented here. Equation (1) is considered to be not applicable for the test results except for the notched compressive and SBS strengths of the T800H/PI-SP composite. They were unchanged with thermal aging time. Meanwhile, Eq. (1) can be applied

for only the data within a limited range of aging time. This problem is left for future investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

The notched tensile, notched compressive, and short beam shear strengths of two kinds of bismaleimide composites and a kind of thermoplastic polyimide composite were investigated at room and thermal aging temperatures, before and after thermal aging, up to 15,000 hours. Major conclusions obtained are as follows:

- (1) In the case of the G40-800/5260 bismaleimide composite, the degradation of notched tensile strength by thermal aging at 120°C was not clear. Although the notched compressive strength at room temperature was not reduced by thermal aging at 120°C, this strength at 120°C slightly decreased after thermal aging of 15,000 hours. The latter fact was also identical for the MR50K/ MR2000N bismaleimide composite.
- (2) Significant reduction was observed in the notched tensile, notched compressive, and SBS strengths of both G40-800/5260 and MR50K/MR2000N composites after thermal aging at 180°C.
- (3) In the case of the G40-800/5260 composite, a small difference between the specimens of two batches appeared in the notched tensile strength and its reduction with thermal aging time.
- (4) The upper limit of practically applicable temperatures for both G40-800/5260 and MR50K/ MR2000N composites is considered to be between 120°C and 180°C, though the notched compressive strength of both materials at 120°C should be investigated, even after thermal aging at 120°C for longer than 15,000 hours.
- (5) In the case of the G40-800/5260 composite, the ascending order of the strength differences at room and aging temperatures, at the same aging time, is notched tensile strength, notched compressive strength, and SBS strength.
- (6) No degradation of notched compressive and SBS strengths was observed for the T800H/PI-SP thermoplastic polyimide composite after thermal aging at 120°C and 180°C up to 15,000 hours.
- (7) Only one kind of oxidation resistant treatment provided a slight improvement of the notched compressive strength of the MR50K/MR2000N composite after thermal aging of 5,000 hours at 180°C.
- (8) Large scatter was observed only in the SBS strength of the MR50K/MR2000N composite after thermal aging at 180°C.
- (9) At least the relationship between strength and thermal aging time, under a constant aging temperature, must be linear on double logarithmic graph paper for an accelerated thermal aging test using a modified Larson-Miller's equation. In the case of thermal aging at 180°C, this kind of relationship was not observed for both bismaleimide composites.

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